

The Universe in its entirety

Its form, beginning, end, and cosmography.
What comes after its end?
Does extraterrestrial life really exist?

“What if the interpretation of astrophysical analyses were wrong and profoundly erroneous?”
“What if the Universe were not only a chemical entity but also a thinking one?”

by Javier Mariscal Estrada
Independent author. Madrid, Spain.
javiermariscalbroker@gmail.com

In this article, I offer a unique opportunity to reveal to everyone what the universe is really like in its entirety, with photos included: its shape, beginning, end, and what comes after its end. And whether there is extraterrestrial life.

Preliminary essay by the author

Great discoveries are a rare phenomenon, and even more so in astrophysics and cosmology, which are limited in their advances by technology and aerospace engineering, limitations that will prevent us from observing the universe in its entirety (not the observable universe).

Based on this premise, astrophysics and cosmology will have to reinterpret their scientific analyses more accurately in order to successfully tackle such an immense challenge as understanding the cosmos in its entirety without having to reach every single corner of it.

History shows us that there are scientific discoveries that were known in the past but could not be approved by the scientific community until scientific pragmatism was put into practice, which does not detract from the fact that the discoveries already existed in the past.

"Leucippus was the one who initiated atomic theory, and his disciple Democritus, a philosopher of the 5th century BC, proposed that reality was made up of atoms and vacuum. However, it was not until 1803 that physicist John Dalton developed the first scientific atomic theory, confirming this idea through inductive and logical reasoning based on observations.

This fact confirms what Albert Einstein said: "Science without philosophy is primitive and confusing; philosophy without science is empty." With this, I want to demonstrate that if philosophy precedes science, when scientists turn it into science, there is 100% accuracy in scientific theory and in the fact itself.

I will give you even more arguments to reinforce the statement I made earlier (keep reading because this is necessary to understand my article). Logic, so necessary for science, can sometimes border on the absurd. Science is based on logical reasoning, but let's listen to this example: a recently retired man commented to a friend that it was a good thing that, when choosing his profession, he listened to his father and not his mother. His friend asked him why, and the man replied, "My father wanted me to be a shoemaker and my mother wanted me to be a dentist. I listened to my father... and in fifty years as a shoemaker, no customer ever came in asking me to fix their teeth."

Science is also based on inductive reasoning, from which it derives its hypotheses and general theories from particular cases. But be careful: something that occurs in a particular case does not necessarily hold true in general, even if it is later verified. Due to the limitations of aerospace engineering and technology, and where mathematics does not reach (singularities), statements that are not correct are sometimes accepted as correct, without knowing it. Thus, what is considered general or a whole, such as the observable universe, may be just a drop of dew in an immense ocean, or, in other words, the observable universe may be a tiny part of a universe of incalculable dimensions.

Through scientific analogy and sensory perception (the same used by Leucippus and Democritus), we will see where the cosmology of the observable universe stands and what data is missing in order to discover the universe in its entirety.

Argument by scientific analogy

The scientific community makes it very clear that the observable universe currently known is to the total universe what a drop of dew is to an immense ocean.

On this basis, let us begin to analyze the similarities between the conclusions drawn by astrophysicists from their analyses and those drawn by geoscientists from theirs, attempting to complement and harmonize them in order to provide a more accurate answer to what is happening and even redefine or change its meaning.

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1. The period that astrophysicists recognize as the oldest in cosmology is the Big Bang, which is defined as a period of very high density and high temperatures that resulted in an expansion that gave rise to the universe. This is completely wrong.

The problem here is that astrophysicists can only observe a very small part of the Total Universe (they only see a drop in the ocean: the observable Universe, figure 1), and this results in limitations in terms of their knowledge and deductions, leading them to the error of thinking that what happens in the observable Universe is a totality when in reality it is what happens in a particle of cosmic dust.

In 1924, Edwin Hubble discovered that the Milky Way was not the only galaxy, but one among many, revealing that the universe was much vaster than previously believed and breaking with the dominant view of the scientific community.

The fixed cosmic space of the entire Universe, formed by low-luminosity intergalactic stars, widely separated from each other and surrounded by immense illuminated darkness, making it a very fascinating area. (It does not collapse because gravitational attraction is very weak on a large scale).

Geoscientists point out that explosions on Earth are caused by a rapid increase in temperature, releasing gases that cause the debris from the explosion to scatter. With these scientific facts, we can redefine the Big Bang theory.

Yes, it was a period of very high density and high temperatures (let's supplement this with geoscience), which caused an explosion that ended when the thermal waves cooled and the objects and elements of the explosion settled within fixed cosmic space: the Universe as a whole.

What astrophysicists are seeing is a tiny part of the sediments, as they recognize: objects, planets, galaxies... and elements, molecular clouds, etc. (Observable Universe) that are part of an immense area that originated as a result of a first explosion and the thermal waves it caused, dragging very large sediments (objects and elements) that were not far apart from each other, creating an area clearly differentiated by its concentric homogeneity (Figure 2).

Recently, elements have been detected in the observable universe that do not fit in. The VirgoHI 25 galaxy, which is a dark galaxy without stars, could be interpreted as a young galaxy, which clearly clashes with the galaxies in our observable universe that are already formed galaxies with stars, or it could be interpreted as a galaxy that does not belong to the cosmographic environment to which it currently belongs.

In geology, when this occurs, materials that are not from the area are called exotic or allochthonous materials because they modify the original geological composition of the area. These materials can be transported from another region by various processes, one of which is movement.

In biological oceanography, when ocean currents, which are massive movements of water driven by varying temperature differences, can displace fish from shallow depths to the surface, removing them from their natural habitat.

And here comes another important detail, which is that it is possible that the VirgoHI 25 galaxy comes from a different area than the one where the sediments from the first explosion or Big Bang were left. This provides us with information about past cosmological processes and another existing cosmological area.

If the first explosion was very strong, according to geology, it could cause the release of thermal waves that alter the composition of other existing elements or objects, and this modification could cause a second explosion, whose force would be less and would cause a dispersion of objects and elements in a different way than the first, with these sediments being smaller and more dispersed among themselves, forming a second area differentiated from the first area created by the first explosion or Big Bang.

This reality clearly clashes with the erroneous theory or interpretation of the Belgian Lemaître (1927), based on redshift data, which proposed that galaxies are moving away from each other, a fact later supported by Hubble's observations (1929), who reported the recession velocities (recession) of galaxies but did not interpret his data as expansion of the universe, using his best telescope of the time, the Hooker (1917).

What physicist Lemaître proposed in 1927 is due to the fact that the data from which he drew that information was taken from scientific observations that had and still have limitations in terms of engineering and aerospace technology, falling into the error of making a very small part of the Universe into a whole.

What can really be deduced from the data collected by Lemaître, bearing in mind that the observable Universe is a particle of cosmic dust within the Universe as a whole, which was moving away due to a constant renewal of a tiny part of the cosmos.

2. The second explosion or second Big Bang (Figure 3) was an explosion that followed the first and differs from it in that its sediments are smaller, further apart, and more dispersed. This second area of the universe is not known and will never be known visually by cosmology (Theia), unless the constructive force of the universe (dark force) brings some object or element from this area closer in its renewal, such as the galaxy VirgoHI 25.

What you are about to see in this working paper does not agree with current deductions in astrophysics and cosmology, so the theory would have to be rearranged or the data collected proven incorrect, even though the theory has solid mathematical foundations.

The first section of this working document, entitled "The Birth of the Universe," presents a very precise interpretive analysis in relation to the rest of the text. It constitutes a profound reflection, the result of well-founded sensitive reasoning, presented with an authority comparable to that of Leucippus and Democritus. (I present here ideas that I consider to be ahead of current scientific understanding and that time will confirm, so that the reader knows where the authority of this analysis comes from).

The birth of the total Universe

Life, which is presence, quality, and generator of life, manifests itself and makes its presence felt in the form of Light: presence because it possesses an electromagnetic field with energy and properties; quality because it interacts with matter, transferring energy and inducing chemical reactions. This Light surrounds darkness and emptiness, which are the absence of Light, and acts upon them by transferring properties to them, the most important of which is **Vital Presence**.

Translated with DeepL.com (free version) This is what scientists study: the origin of life based on the natural laws and processes of the Universe, even though they cannot explain the first cause that made it possible.

Therefore, darkness and emptiness represent approximately 95% of cosmic space, and only 5% is visible. These data, obtained from the observable universe, can be extrapolated to the universe as a whole.

Figure A

The shape of the total Universe and its cosmology

The reason why the entire Universe has a vertical rectangular shape when viewed from the front and a circular projection when viewed from above is because Light, the form in which Life manifested itself, follows a straight and shortest path and, as it is located above darkness and emptiness, it projects its influence downward, while darkness, emptiness, and visible matter are arranged under its action. This coincides with what neuroscience confirms: those who experience leaving their body and returning describe seeing a Light at the end of a tunnel (figure A).

“This phenomenon described by neuroscience not only confirms individual experience, but also corroborates the universal structure presented here, where Light marks the way and reveals the true form of the Universe.”

The shape of the Universe seen from the front is vertical rectangular, on which all the elements and matter in the total Universe are distributed. The creative Force (dark force and dark matter) is responsible for this cosmological distribution.

This force causes several things, the first of which is that it shapes the course of the universe or, in other words, sculpts and molds the Cosmos wherever it passes, with elements and objects, giving it form and, consequently, a beginning and an end.

Shape of the entire Universe seen from the front, with the direction of the creative Force.

The shape of the entire universe seen from above does not have a spiral shape, nor does it have that white light in the center, but it does have a sense of depth.

It would be reasonable to compare it to the current of a river that originates from the force of gravity or to a highway: there is only one direction, no exits, and no turning back.

Just as in a river the current is determined by the force of gravity, in the Universe there is an origin or source that determines the force that moves, organizes, and projects all matter and energy upward.

Dark matter—although invisible, it is fiery in color; somewhat similar to what happens with white light, which seems simple but hides many colors (keeping distances in mind)—is the dense body or substance of emptiness and darkness, which sustains, nourishes, regenerates, and keeps everything in place, and through which the creative force (dark force) flows. This force is intelligent (theory of physicist Bobby Azarian, who proposes that the universe is a thinking being, which is why the Hadron generator does not give the results they are looking for, because there is intelligence and therefore different reactions in identical processes; one could say that this generator is a lifeless Frankenstein) and also acts as a guardian; nothing happens without it being present, or in other words, it is the creator of the laws of physics and natural processes by which the entire universe is governed.

An example of this can be related to the study of slits in quantum physics, where identical particles exhibit different behaviors depending on how the experiment is observed, analogous to how cosmic force interacts intelligently with bodies. Specifically, the entire Universe was designed from the top down, but its vital functioning is from the bottom up.

Before the Big Bang

The Big Bang was not the absolute beginning: before it, there were luminous structures—not stars like those we know today, but giant energetic entities—some of which collapsed, triggering the Big Bang and scattering primordial matter. Others, however, did not collapse: they survived with weakened light that dimly illuminates the static Universe. That dim light, even older than the observable Universe, filtered into the new space, becoming the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB).

The Big Bang

The Big Bang is part of the cosmology of the universe; it is not the universe in its entirety nor the origin of the universe, but rather a small part surrounding the Earth, whose first explosion within cosmic space created a great diversification of concentrated objects and elements, in addition to the planet Earth. The second explosion, smaller and more distant, created the same but smaller and more diversified, creating the moon (Theia), with the two explosions being complementary and creating the same cosmology in the cosmos near Earth.

The Big Bang ended when its creative cycle was complete. The universe concentrated around the Earth (observable universe) is not expanding but constantly regenerating, with upward movements of force (creative force) and downward movements of objects and elements (the creative force allows each element or object that forms the universe to interrelate). The rest of cosmic space is static. There were two explosions because the sediments left by the explosions are concentrated in different spaces, their size varying in nature and order according to their location.

The initial Big Bang (Fig. 2) created a dense core that exploded, forming the first cosmic structures in a specific area (Fig. 3). Some of the matter did not explode immediately, but did so later in another region, generating galaxies and clusters at different times and places.

This suggests distinct dense cores and staggered expansions, which could explain why two-thirds of galaxies rotate clockwise and one-third counterclockwise, their distribution in different planes (some vertical, others horizontal), and why some galaxies are younger and others older.

“The peculiar nature of the Great Attractor suggests that it could come from the explosion of the second density zone, influencing the local gravitational flow.”

Black holes

Black holes are dark matter in a different arrangement in the universe, that is, dark force generates converging currents (don't forget that dark force is intelligent) with the function of renewing cosmology, either by absorbing the core of a supernova (spaghettification), or by wanting to unite large areas with gravitational attraction (the Great Attractor), but their function is to maintain the biome of the cosmos.

The Theory of Everything

The theory of everything, whose main objective is to unify general relativity (the force of gravity of the macrocosm) with quantum mechanics (forces at the atomic and subatomic levels), will not happen because they cannot be unified, since the four forces of the universe depend on cosmic intelligence, which has the ability to adapt efficiently to the cosmological environment. The four forces revolve around Intelligence, which disposes of them.

The fundamental forces are not separate entities, but rather different expressions of structured emptiness. Emptiness is not what remains when we remove everything, but rather what allows everything to exist.

As in Fibonacci, where the part relates to the whole without containing it, forces and gravity also show links without unifying. Intelligence is what achieves this synthesis, which would explain why experiments such as ALICE do not reproduce the same results on Earth as in the cosmos.

The same thing happens with the four elements on Earth: earth, water, fire, and air. It is not that there is a fifth element, but rather that these four elements revolve around cosmic intelligence.

The Theory of Relativity, a beloved illusion

Dark matter holds the entire universe together, which is why light is deflected, the movements of stars and the flow of time do not depend on gravity curving space-time. Light is deflected in galaxy clusters and gas disks around black holes not by gravity, but by the arrangement of this matter. The 1970 experiment showed that stars at the edges of galaxies rotate like those at the core, confirming that gravity does not dominate. GPS clocks flow in time according to the density of dark matter and cosmic consciousness, not because of the curvature of space. (That is why there are so many singularities, errors).

Matter does not tell space-time how to curve, nor does space-time tell matter how to move; this concept is erroneous. Universal consciousness is what lengthens or shortens time, in the interaction that is occurring in the cosmos, depending on whether it moves away or closer.

The Vital Presence

The Vital Presence is the emanation of Life within darkness and emptiness; a vital halo that keeps everything in existence. It is to the Universe what the soul is to human beings: without it, everything would fade away and cease to exist. (Not observable).

Why does the universe exist? And why is there no extraterrestrial life?

I have to say that I don't see the scientific community asking this question, rather they ask how it originated but not why the universe exists.

The first answer is simple: there doesn't have to be a reason. It must be said that the universe itself is an entity that has its own beauty, its own fragrance, and that it has been realized.

But let's develop it just in case there is a reason. First, let's imagine that we want to hide a treasure in a piece of land in a region and we commission a cartographer to make a detailed map of the region, the area, and the location of the treasure. I give this map to the owner of the treasure and say, "Here is the map of your treasure." But of course, the owner is rightly angry and tells me that he cannot see where the treasure is buried. Of course, the cartographer has not put it there, so no matter how amazing the treasure map is, if the treasure is not there, there is no treasure and no map.

*The same applies to the universe: if there is no treasure to enjoy it, **what use is the universe if there is no one to contemplate it?***

The universe unfolds with reference to the Earth, that is, its limits and its cosmography, those of the total universe (not the observable universe) are established with reference to the Earth, its treasure, which is why I disagree with astrophysicists when they say that human beings are insignificant in comparison with the universe. In saying this, they fail to take into account that the greatness of things is not seen in their size but in their potential or their realization, in what they are or simply in the mystery they hold within.

*The fact that the universe only has the Earth as a reference in its construction proves that there is **no extraterrestrial life or intelligent life outside of it**. This resolves the paradox posed by Italian physicist Enrico Fermi in 1950.*

Human beings are the only creatures that hold a secret within themselves and have the choice, through consciousness and inner reflection, to distance themselves from their animal nature, draw closer to their inner selves, to the divine, see it, and then dissolve into the mystery of life, becoming part of the mystery of the Universe.

In addition, the universe also has the function of promoting curiosity among the scientific community, so that through their scientific studies they can show other humans how fortunate we are to be part of such a majestic work.

This is proof that the entire Universe unfolded with the Earth as its reference point: "It took less than an hour to form atoms, hundreds of millions of years to form stars and planets, and billions of years to form humanity." George Gamow (1952).

CONSCIOUSNESS is the origin of the Universe.

Cosmography of the Universe

In this section, we must bear in mind one thing: the human and technological limitations that scientists will always face when studying the universe.

Human beings have no limits (they are the only element in the universe that has no limits), but scientists do, and when faced with such a great work as the universe, they will always be at a disadvantage when it comes to studying and understanding it. That is why the universe makes available to them, in a small strip of the cosmos that is unfathomable to scientists, a series of concentrated events (the Big Bang) so that they can see its majesty. That strip is very small, but astrophysicists have not yet reached even the smallest percentage of what can be reached.

In summary, the cosmology of the universe is distributed in such a way that the parts closest to Earth and also the most distant parts, which scientists cannot reach but which are close to Earth,

the mysteries to be solved are concentrated, and little by little those mysteries fade away until they reach a point where cosmic space is a backdrop of stars and darkness until its end, which is not a limit. That space within the universe is so far away that it is absurd to include as many details as at the beginning if no one is going to contemplate or study it.

The Big Bang was an explosion that ended at its moment, and the force of the universe moves, regenerates, and removes all the sediments that the explosion caused. The force of the universe ensures that the piece of space where the explosion occurred is always there, regenerating itself. The universe is not in turmoil or in a violent state; on the contrary, it is in balance and silence.

What is the end of the universe like? And the beginning?

As I said earlier, when the universe reaches its end, in a very large space or area, the universe becomes diluted in terms of mysteries but not in terms of beauty. It is only made up of stars and darkness, and there is no regeneration; it is constantly the same.

And it is here, at the end of that zone, where the universe ends and a small strip begins, without stars, without light, without space, there is nothing, only a void and darkness that do not exist anywhere else, that is, its origin is the same as its end (remember how the beginning or birth of the universe originated), and this is the furthest place you can reach with Earth as a reference point. Or, to explain it another way: those who experience leaving their body and returning describe seeing a light at the end of a tunnel (neuroscience). They returned because the door that opened and showed them the Light closed behind them.

The beginning of the universe is very close to Earth compared to its end, but it is unfathomable to scientists and technology. You could say that it is just as far away as the end in terms of the possibility of reaching it. It is an area that starts small and grows, from being static to the Big Bang 1 and 2, once again offering many mysteries to be discovered.

Author's note

I decided to share my knowledge because I have observed that, around the Universe, mysteries upon mysteries are created— Enrico Fermi's Paradox, Dark Forest, Fast Radio Bursts, the "Wow!" signal, Big Crunch, Big Bounce, Big Bang, cosmic expansion and cosmic inflation, the Bubble Universe theory, isotropy, singularity, and even the misconception of an infinite universe — often mixed with false interpretations.

The shape of the universe is exactly as I have shown you in this article. Some details of the supports I have created may contain inaccuracies, but the essence and images reflect what the universe is really like in its entirety.

"You cannot force the universe to fit into a mold that does not belong to it. If we look at it only from a scientific-mathematical angle, we lose its true nature: poetry, beauty, and fragrance." The universe is not only measured, it is also contemplated, felt, and lived.

Science, both present and future, will never know it: neither its beginning, nor its end, nor its shape, nor its true color, nor its total dimensions, nor the intelligent creative force that makes everything happen before physical laws and natural processes.

Clarification *This sentence: "Those who experience leaving their body and returning describe seeing a light at the end of a tunnel" (neuroscience) can be explained as follows: two things happen. The first is that they travel through the entire Universe at such speed that they cross such an immense distance in seconds; that is why they see a tunnel, when in reality they are traveling through the entire Universe in that brief instant. They perceive the light because the door at the end of the Universe, located in another plane-space, has opened for them for a few moments. When it closes, they are forced to return to their point of origin: the bodies from which they came. Those who pass through it never return.*

All this happens through the dark force, which allows the outward journey to take place in a few seconds and the return to happen instantaneously, which shows that time can be lengthened or shortened depending on that intelligent force (Theory of Relativity).

Map of the universe

Note: *The proportion of the observable universe to the actual totality of the universe would be comparable to that of a drop of dew in an immense ocean.*

The total universe is so enormous that no science or technology—no matter how bold—will ever be able to encompass it. It is an immensity that will forever exceed the reach of man... but not his inner self, because there are no boundaries there.

FINAL CONCLUSION

Governments and political powers, such as those linked to CERN, control much scientific and technological research, sometimes referred to as “hadron generators” because of their capacity for appropriation and control. These projects, funded and promoted by strategic military agencies, remain hidden behind the label of “fundamental research” and have dual applications that include surveillance, influence, and resource extraction, demonstrating how science can become an instrument of destructive power, as was the case with the atomic bomb.

The universe protects itself through dark matter, dark energy, and cosmic consciousness, creating **illusions and misperceptions**, such as the false dominance of space-time curvature, the misinterpretation of the Big Bang, and the mirages of cosmic expansion. It limits our perception of light to hide dark matter and causes reality to change as it is observed, as shown by the slit experiments and the Josephson experiment. In addition, it extends enormous distances within the universe to prevent its direct study.

Dark matter and dark energy, present even within us at the atomic level, **adapt each being to its function** in order to maintain universal balance: bees perceive ultraviolet light to pollinate, and snakes detect heat to hunt. Each organism receives what it needs to survive and sustain the homeostasis of the universe.

Applying Enrico Fermi's paradox to Earth, humanity has reached advanced levels of technology on several occasions, but previous civilizations were **destroyed 83 times** by the misuse of their technology, leaving only vestiges such as the pyramids to warn us of what happened in the past. This shows that technological evolution can be interrupted when used destructively.

Miquel Pérez-Sánchez Pla – Architect, Doctor of Architecture (UPC), Poet, and Egyptologist. In his work *La Gran Pirámide, clave secreta del pasado* (*The Great Pyramid, Secret Key to the Past*), he argues that the Egyptian pyramids contain advanced knowledge of mathematics, geometry, astronomy, geodesy, history, language, and numerous cross-referenced data, including a secret code linking them to Atlantis. These constructions demonstrate a level of technology and planning **far superior to what was believed possible at the time (neither the pulley nor the wheel were known)**, with perfect cuts in enormous blocks of stone and precise measurements that anticipated concepts such as the number Pi, the meter, the Greek language, the movement of the planets, etc.

The Sphinx, built before the pyramids, suggests knowledge of planetary movements prior to the 19th century. The star channels in the pyramids allowed future dates of important events to be marked, integrating astronomical observation and temporal calculation into architecture.

It is believed **that this information came from civilizations prior to the Egyptian one**, which passed on their knowledge to those who built the pyramids, thus leaving a legacy of wisdom for future generations.

Ultimately, the universe only reveals itself as it is to the innocent, through experiential knowledge, which is why mystics know it.

Three unresolved problems in modern cosmology: the beginning of the universe, the temporal singularity of the Big Bang, and the wave function

The first thing to consider is that there are two complementary views of the universe, historically recognized without excluding each other.

On the one hand, **Albert Einstein**, defender of a universe built on darkness, emptiness, and matter, governed by physical laws and natural processes that can be formulated and measured: the physical halo of the universe.

On the other hand, **Rabindranath Tagore**, for whom reality acquires its full meaning through life, experience, and consciousness, dimensions that cannot be directly measured and that make up the halo of mystery of the universe.

The two perspectives on the universe: the scientific and the mystical

Einstein wrote: **“The most beautiful experience we can have is the mysterious. It is the fundamental emotion that stands at the cradle of true art and true science.”**

He pointed out that science alone cannot grasp all aspects of reality; there are dimensions of the universe **that cannot be directly measured** and require experience, intuition, or deep understanding.

Tagore said: **“When the mystery is small, it is clear as the water in a glass; when the mystery is great, like the universe, it becomes dark and difficult to see.”**

One says it is not measurable and the other that it is difficult to see, but neither denies it.

Problem 1 and 2: the beginning of the universe and the temporal singularity of the Big Bang

Standard cosmology asserts that the universe is born from a **temporal singularity**, a point without cause or laws from which everything emerges through a kind of **mathematical magic**. To sustain this impossible beginning, **cosmic inflation** is introduced, an **arbitrary** expansion added a posteriori to make the model work. The entire edifice rests on **beautiful but false equations**, because they start from an origin that is neither understood nor resolved. The **JWST** is showing that when the foundation is unreal, no mathematical sophistication can save the theory. (**Mon Z14**).

As **Roger Penrose** has pointed out, science needs risky ideas, because conventional ones don't work. A radical and bold, even "crazy" vision is required when the molds we have created do not fit the reality of the universe.

Let's begin: the observable universe is not the total universe; it is only the part we can measure, a drop of dew in an immense ocean. Confusing the two is the first fundamental error of cosmology.

What Rabindranath Tagore describes is not poetry detached from reality, but the very structure of the universe expressed from consciousness. When he states that mystery, when it becomes immense, becomes obscure and difficult to see, he is pointing to a region without light, without activity, and without regeneration. Tagore expresses this from inner experience; here it is presented as a concrete cosmological structure. These are not two different visions, but the same reality described with complementary languages.

The difference is not in what is described, but in the language used to describe it.

To understand the observable universe and avoid conceptual errors, we must begin with the true origin of the Total Universe, which contains the observable universe.

In the dimension where the total universe currently exists, there was only **darkness and emptiness**, an absence of light and activity—in other words, nothingness. From another dimension, **Light emerges**, which is **presence, quality, and creator of life**. That presence endows the physical dimension—darkness, emptiness, inactivity, and nothingness—with **light, energy, and activity**, and brings the mystery of the other dimension: **life, consciousness, and self-observation**, thus unifying the **physical and the non-physical**.

The universe is endowed **with everything necessary to create itself, integrating the physical and the non-physical: dark matter**. In the physical realm are the four fundamental forces: **strong nuclear, weak nuclear, electromagnetic, and gravity**. In the non-physical realm, three forces operate: **the force of creation, the force of maintenance or regeneration, and the force of elimination**, which allow for the formation, conservation, and continuous transformation of the universe.

The first philosopher to ask the question "why is there something rather than nothing?" was **Parmenides** (approx. 515–450 BC), who reflected on existence and the impossibility of nothingness. This question is resolved by considering the **complementary** sides, the **heads and tails of the same coin: darkness**, the absence of light, and **light**, presence; **nothingness**, the absence of activity, and **something**, activity. These dualities coexist and form the basis on which

the observable universe is built and what transcends it, integrating the physical and the non-physical. If you recognize nothing, you implicitly recognize something.

Zarathustra symbolizes the human being who takes responsibility for his actions without resorting to a supreme being. In this cosmological model, the creative Light does not remain in the universe: it fulfills its original function and withdraws to its own dimension, leaving an autonomous, coherent, and self-aware cosmos (in the sense of Nietzsche's famous formulation: "God is dead").

I previously explained my own view on why the universe is rectangular in shape, but this time I will use the definition of physicist Arthur M. Young. In conclusion, the total universe takes on a rectangular shape because 4 represents the level where reality becomes finite, limited, and concrete. This "framework" allows objects to exist, integrating the physical and non-physical dimensions and reflecting the structure necessary for the universe to manifest and evolve. (The four sides of the rectangle). Length, width, depth, and time.

Once the universe takes shape, giant energetic entities emerge, pre-existing the Big Bang, interacting with their environment as dinosaurs did on Earth, shaping and transforming the cosmos. Some collapsed, preparing the space for the Big Bang and sowing primordial matter, while others survived with weakened light, forming the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB).

The Big Bang is not the absolute beginning or the total universe, but a localized part of the cosmos. It occurred in two complementary explosions, in different phases or times, which diversified and distributed matter in different spaces according to its size, nature, and order. These explosions completed their creative cycle, giving rise to the observable universe, where matter moves under forces of creation, regeneration, and elimination, while the rest of space remains static and illuminated by the faint light of the giant energy entities that did not collapse.

*With this, **the temporal singularity of the Big Bang is resolved**: giant energy entities prepared space, Light endowed the physical dimension with energy and activity, and **the two complementary explosions in different phases generated** the observable universe. What science interprets as expansion, according to what the **JWST** is finding, is actually **regeneration: upward movements and downward interaction**, because the force in the universe acts only upward, mixing and diversifying the elements of both explosions.*

In this framework, MON z14 does not contradict the Big Bang: it contradicts the misidentification of the CMB as its beginning. By separating the two phenomena, the temporal conflict disappears and the paradox of "too early" galaxies is resolved. The Big Bang is not the origin of time, and the CMB is not its signature. The Big Bang is a later, local, and finite creative phase, and MON z14 is consistent, not anomalous.

The CMB is not the remnant light of the Big Bang, but the faint emission of giant energetic entities that pre-existed the Big Bang. Each of these entities radiates its own light, and from Earth they are perceived as a microwave background with small variations in temperature and polarization.

*The CMB light ceases to be a signal from the Big Bang and becomes a **record of pre-universal entities**, naturally explaining the observed inequalities without entering into temporal paradoxes or contradictions with "too early" galaxies such as MON z14.*

*Einstein and Tagore agree on the essentials: there is a part of the universe that is real but not measurable; one says it cannot be measured, the other that it is difficult to see, but neither denies it. At that boundary, another form of knowledge appears. After decades of study, doctors Raymond Moody and Manuel Sans Segarra have collected testimonies from clinically dead patients who coincide, without prior agreement, in the same experience: **a light at the end of the***

tunnel. When scientific measurement is no longer possible, the universe communicates in another way. To understand it in its entirety, it is not enough to demonstrate: one must also listen.

Roger Penrose points the way: when conventional physics is not enough, it is necessary to explore risky ideas. **Arthur M. Young and Itzhak Bentov** move in the same direction, expanding science toward the deep structure of the universe and its link to consciousness. In another vein, **Tagore, Zarathustra,** and other mystics access the same knowledge, becoming a living expression of the totality of the universe. Their definitions seem like poetry, but they are only direct descriptions of what they see.

Although the **theory of relativity** and phenomena such as **atomic clocks** or **redshift** are useful for describing local processes, they cease to be applicable **in the temporal singularity of the Big Bang and in the spatial singularity of black holes.** All of this belongs to local science, limited to the observable universe and **not to the total universe.** The supposed “expansion” is actually a **process of regeneration of elements,** resulting from different **phases and explosions,** which mix matter from different times and places, also explaining observations such as those of **MON z14.** The analogy of the inflating balloon is a **misleading simplification** that does not reflect the true structure or dynamics of the cosmos.

Problem 3: The wave function

Every particle in the universe acts as if it possessed consciousness: it knows that in its natural environment—the entire cosmos—it must manifest itself in the way that is already pre-imprinted on it. The force that causes the collapse of its wave function occurs in the past, following a global decision that ensures the coherence of the universe. Thus, the collapse is neither random nor local, but rather the present manifestation of that pre-established history. Born's rule only describes probabilities in isolated laboratories, disconnected from their natural environment, as in the case of nuclear fusion, and therefore does not reflect universal reality. No small local event can generate the butterfly effect that destabilizes the cosmos: each result obeys the global coherence and balance of the universe.

The real questions are avoided: the equations don't add up and paradoxes abound. We don't know what causes the **collapse of the wave function,** how the **temporal singularity** of the Big Bang is resolved, or what a **beginning** means. Consensus theories and beautiful equations are built on these gaps. The JWST demonstrates that, by ignoring these problems, everything that is accepted fails in the face of reality.

I have presented truths about the universe that can be explained and understood, because the mind can see them but they cannot be formulated, because, as **Kurt Gödel,** one of the greatest logicians and mathematicians of the 20th century, pointed out, every logical and complex system

contains truths that cannot be proven from within, **BUT THE HUMAN MIND CAN UNDERSTAND TRUTHS THAT ARE ACCEPTED WITHOUT PROOF**; the universe is one of those systems AND THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY insists on proving something that computation cannot, but the mind recognizes as truth. As Roger Penrose says, science needs risky ideas because sensible ones solve nothing. The time has come to consider what seems impossible: we need a crazy idea, a radical vision of reality, because the conventional ones, accepted by the scientific community, do not work in the face of what the JWST reveals.

Axiom: there are fundamental truths that cannot be proven; they are recognized.